

Do Climate Extremes Result in More Ambitious Mitigation and Adaptation Climate Policy?

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Abstract

A common assumption in both scholarly and policy debates is that climate extremes can spur more ambitious climate policies. Here, we conduct a comparative narrative review of research on how climate extremes affect both mitigation and adaptation policy change. We find that empirical support for this assumption remains limited and that its theoretical foundations require further development. Drawing on the review, supplemented by illustrative empirical analyses, we show that climate extremes are unlikely to trigger major increases in mitigation policy ambition but are more plausibly linked to shifts in adaptation policy. Importantly, the mechanisms through which climate extremes shape adaptation policy ambition remain underexplored. Building on our review, we propose a research framework that distinguishes the political economy of mitigation and adaptation. We argue that adaptation policies are more responsive to climate extremes because of key differences in the distribution of costs and benefits. Particularly in polarized contexts, the often rather localized benefits and diffused costs of adaptation may create political pathways for strategic sequencing and packaging of adaptation and mitigation policies, ultimately advancing climate policy ambition.

Introduction

Climate change is poised to exacerbate the frequency and intensity of extreme climate and weather events, leading to severe socio-economic impacts of such climate extremes¹ across the world, affecting most of the human population¹⁻³. India, for instance, has endured a severe and prolonged heatwave in 2024, with temperatures soaring above 50 degrees Celsius in numerous regions. In September and October 2024, record-breaking rainfall and storms led to severe flooding in central Europe and Spain, while the United States (US) suffered from the consequences of the hurricanes Helene and Milton and large wildfires. Clearly, these impacts underline the urgent need to reduce CO₂ emissions and adapt communities to become more resilient through decisive climate policy actions⁴⁻⁶. In the face of the detrimental socio-economic impacts of climate extremes, an increasing number of scholars and policymakers have discussed if and how such climate extremes will act as catalysts for the adoption of more ambitious (i.e., stringent)² climate change mitigation (i.e., efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions) and adaptation (i.e., efforts to adjust to the impacts of climate change) policies^{9-16,6,17}. For instance, climate extremes may increase policy ambitions by shifting public opinion and discourses^{18,19} and by fostering the development of new political coalitions in favor of more ambitious climate change mitigation and adaptation policies due to increasingly visible climate change-related economic damages and casualties^{6,20}.

Theoretically, the larger visibility and urgency of climate extremes – e.g., in the form of extreme heat (Figure 1) – could serve as focal points in media, public, and political debates, potentially opening windows of opportunity for escalating climate policy ambition^{13,21,6}. However, as of 2025 the political momentum does not suggest rapidly increasing climate policy ambition in many countries. Specifically, we lack comparative evidence if and how the socio-economic impacts of climate extremes result in more ambitious mitigation and/or adaptation policies^{6,9-16}.

Figure 1: Do climate change and climate extremes result in increased climate change mitigation and/or adaptation policy ambition? (A) Global mean surface temperature change compared to 1850-1900²² (B) Share of world population exposed to hot days ($T_{max} > 35^{\circ}\text{C}$) between 1979 and 2023²³.

¹ In line with the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), the term 'climate extremes' is used here for simplicity to refer to 'extreme weather and extreme climate events,' as defined in the [IPCC Glossary](#).

² In line with the policy design literature, we differentiate here between policy density (i.e., number of policies) and the policy ambition (i.e., stringency/intensity of policies)^{7,8}

In this article, we contribute to this ongoing debate about the political and policy effects of climate extremes in several ways. First, we conduct the – to our knowledge – first comparative narrative review²⁴ of the existing literature (see Supplemental Information, Section A) on the effects of climate extremes on both climate change mitigation and adaptation policy change. In particular, we offer a narrative review and novel comparative synthesis of insights on the political mechanisms linking climate extremes to both mitigation and adaptation policy change. Our narrative review finds no robust empirical evidence to suggest that climate extremes significantly influence *mitigation* policy ambitions, even though they can have political effects – such as (often short-term) changes in public opinion and voting behaviors. Additionally, the narrative review of existing research highlights a critical gap in the literature regarding the relationship between climate extremes and adaptation policy ambition, particularly emphasizing the serious bias of existing literature on the EU/US context. Our narrative review also emphasizes the absence of comparative panel datasets tracking mitigation and adaptation policy ambition across regions and for developing countries' contexts where climate impacts will likely be greatest. More research is also needed on the political mechanisms that link climate extremes to adaptation policy change at different levels of government, especially in developing countries where research on this link is particularly scarce, even though developing countries are often particularly exposed to climate change impacts.

Second, to complement the narrative review, we present data-driven empirical illustrations of how mitigation policy ambition has evolved in relation to climate extremes across countries over time, supported by illustrative qualitative case studies on the effects of climate extremes on both mitigation and adaptation policy. Our findings provide a more nuanced perspective, indicating that the influence of climate extremes on mitigation policy ambition in high-emitting countries is limited. In contrast, their impact on adaptation policy appears stronger but warrants further investigation based on new harmonized datasets on adaptation policy ambition.

Third, building on our narrative review and illustrative analysis, we propose a theoretical framework for future research on the political and policy effects of climate extremes. We argue that while climate extremes are unlikely to drive significant changes in mitigation policies, more frequent and intense climate extremes may prompt the adoption of more ambitious climate adaptation policies, which often lead to rather concentrated benefits but more diffused costs. Furthermore, climate extremes might open novel opportunities for *strategic coalition building, sequencing and packaging of mitigation and adaptation policies* – especially in more polarized contexts and in international climate politics.

Research challenge: Do climate extremes result in more ambitious mitigation and adaptation climate policy?

Our narrative review identified various political mechanisms through which climate extremes potentially can affect climate change mitigation and adaptation policy ambition: (a) elevating public and (social) media discourses, for instance via increased salience of climate change, (b) altering mass public beliefs and actions, such as public opinion, voting behaviors, or social movements, or (c) changing elite actor positions, such as interest group and party positions.

Discourse effects

While mitigation policy changes arguably require the attribution of climate extremes to climate change, adaptation policy changes can take place without explicitly linking such extreme events to climate change. Research on the relationship between climate extremes and public discourse, however, reveals that climate extremes frequently amplify discussions on climate change. For instance, panel data analyses show that major hurricanes in the US between 2010 and 2022 significantly increased the salience of climate change in media coverage, particularly in regions directly affected by these events²⁵. Similar patterns have been observed in Europe, where short-term temperature anomalies strongly influenced media discourse²⁶ and social media analyses found a strong correlation between extreme temperatures and climate-related tweets²⁷. However, this increased salience of climate change in discourses is often temporally and geographically constrained, typically dissipating within a couple of weeks after the event^{28,29}

Furthermore, social media and newspaper analyses in Anglo-Saxon countries indicate that actors in climate movements tend to link climate change more strongly to climate extremes in social media than articles in major news outlets do³⁰. The effects of climate extremes on (local) discourses also often depend on the prior opinion and partisanship of communities, e.g., with Democratic-leaning and highly educated communities in the US showing stronger engagement³¹. Additionally, repeated exposure to climate extremes may lead to a "boiling frog" effect, where the perception of abnormal climate conditions diminishes over time, even as concern over climate extremes persists³². Therefore, repeated exposure and social normalization processes may obscure public awareness of the link between anthropogenic climate change and its impacts³².

Mass public effects

Generally, there is more research on the mass public effects of climate extremes compared to studies on discourse, party and interest group effects. Especially, we know more about the effects of climate extremes on public support for mitigation rather than adaptation policy^{33,34}. Existing reviews on such mass public effects of climate extremes reveal mixed evidence, with many studies reporting weak effects on citizens' climate beliefs and mitigation policy support³⁵⁻⁴¹. Yet, most existing studies use observational methods and look at stated preferences rather than revealed behaviors³⁵. Several experimental public opinion studies demonstrate that news on climate extremes and the temporal proximity of severe climate change impacts do not significantly affect the perceived urgency of climate change action and policy support,

especially for more costly climate change mitigation policies⁴². While other studies show that personal experiences with climate extremes can heighten environmental concerns and policy support, these effects tend to be rather short-lived^{19,31,43,44}. For instance, in 2022 exposure to Hurricane Ian increased concern and policy support of personally affected US residents but this effect decayed within 6 months.

The extent to which individuals attribute climate extremes to climate change plays a critical role in shaping their policy attitudes. Yet, the strength of citizens' attribution of climate extremes to climate change varies between countries and regions⁴⁵. For instance, surveys in the US indicate that approximately two-thirds of citizens recognize climate change as a contributing factor to climate extremes⁴⁶. Attribution effects and increased concern about climate change are particularly pronounced in regions directly affected by extreme weather⁴⁷. Across 12 European countries temperature increases by 5 °C relative to normal temperatures in the preceding 30 years have raised climate concern by up to one percentage point⁴⁸, while in the US even larger effects of climate extremes on climate concern are found¹⁸.

However, cognitive biases, political ideology, and social norms strongly moderate these effects^{31,49,50}. For instance, the connections between climate change and climate extremes are most prevalent among voters with a high pre-existing belief in climate change, if the event had substantial impacts and elite actors attributed the event to climate change^{50,51}. Such motivated reasoning is also apparent with respect to the effects of climate extremes weather events on individuals' willingness to pay for climate change mitigation policy. For instance, in the US people who experienced climate extremes, especially wildfires, are willing to pay around \$71 to \$106 per ton CO₂e more for mitigation policies, compared to individuals who did not experience such events, yet these effects are much stronger among Democrat voters and individuals, who believe climate change is human-caused⁵².

Similarly, exposure to extreme temperatures, wildfires, and floods can increase pro-environmental voting, but such effects are often context-dependent and stronger among voters already predisposed to supporting climate change mitigation^{43,53,54}. For example, research in California demonstrates that proximity to wildfires increased support for climate-related ballot measures in Democratic-leaning areas but had little to no effect in Republican-leaning regions⁵³. Analyses in Sweden indicate that wildfires led to a measurable increase in Green Party vote share at both national and local levels, while incumbent parties often faced electoral losses in affected areas⁵⁵. In Denmark and Germany, flooding events have been associated with increased support for pro-climate parties, though these effects are inconsistent and dependent on the flooding severity and the specific context⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸. More recently, it has been shown⁵⁹ that in EU countries grievance about the economic losses occurred due to climate extremes drive voters – especially in more vulnerable regions and if they are not insured against such losses – to punish incumbents and support populist parties. In contrast, green parties tend to gain support primarily in wealthier, urban, and more loss insured regions where climate change issues are prioritized and climate extremes have less direct negative economic effects on

voters⁵⁹. However, it is important to highlight that such potential context-dependent and often short-lived shifts in voting behaviors do not necessarily translate into climate policy changes.

Unlike for mitigation policy, we still lack important longitudinal and comparative evidence on how climate extremes affect public support and voting behaviors for different types of adaptation policies across regions and levels of government. Existing public opinion studies suggest that individuals who have recently experienced such events exhibit higher levels of support for climate adaptation policies^{34,35,60,61}. However, the findings also indicate that this relationship is relatively weak, varies across individuals' predispositions, and diminishes over time³⁴. Additionally, how adaptation policies are framed – whether as responses to "climate change" or "extreme weather" – can significantly shape public support, with conservatives exhibiting greater willingness to support adaptation policies when framed around extreme weather, while liberals show stronger backing when linked explicitly to climate change^{62,63}.

Finally, sporadic environmental disasters have historically mobilized change-oriented social movements, such as opposition to nuclear energy⁶⁴ and calls for stricter regulation of oil infrastructure⁶⁵. Yet, it remains unclear if more frequent and severe climate extremes foster the development of climate change mitigation and adaptation policy movements.

Party and interest group effects

The influence of climate extremes on elite actors (e.g., political parties and interest groups) is another channel through which climate extremes can potentially affect climate change mitigation and adaptation policy ambition. In the EU, climate extremes have led to short-term increases in Green Parties' press releases on the environment and climate policy but this effect is not sustained for a long period nor does it affect other parties⁶⁶. Partisan effects of climate extremes are also shown in legislators' decisions to sponsor climate policy-related bills^{67,68}. In the US, for example, local temperature anomalies have influenced climate policy sponsorship among Democratic legislators but not their Republican counterparts⁶⁹. More broadly, politicians often avoid directly linking extreme weather to climate change, particularly in politically polarized contexts where doing so may entail electoral risks⁶³. Moreover, there is limited knowledge about how elite actors, such as parties and interest groups, shift their beliefs and positions on adaptation rather than mitigation policy in response to climate extremes⁷⁰. Important gaps also remain in the context of more affected and developing countries.

Effects on mitigation policy ambition

In addition to the political mechanisms through which climate extremes might affect mitigation and adaptation policy, scholars also evaluated whether climate extremes result in policy changes. However, most of these case studies focus on how climate extremes affect changes in mitigation rather than adaptation policies and yield mixed results. Some case studies suggest that climate extremes might spur climate change mitigation reforms. In India, for instance, increased media attention to climate change following climate extremes has been linked to improvements in the country's Climate Change Performance Index^{71,72}. Similarly, in the UK, the experience of severe flooding in 2007 contributed to stronger government commitments to

emissions reduction and the adoption of the Climate Change Act⁷². However, only a few comparative large-n analyses on the climate change mitigation policy effects of extreme weather effects exist, which paint a more nuanced picture. One study⁶ examining temperature shocks and natural disasters across multiple countries between 1990 and 2018 found no significant impact of climate extremes on climate change mitigation policies. Another large-n study⁹ suggests that only well-functioning democracies tend to adopt mitigation policies in response to climate extremes, with less democratic nations showing negligible effects.

A recent panel study examining policy density – rather than policy ambition – as the outcome variable¹⁷ finds that climate-related disasters lead to an increase in mitigation laws, but predominantly in countries projected to experience the most severe future climate damages. This effect is further amplified in democratic contexts, suggesting an interaction between vulnerability and political regime type¹⁷. Compared to earlier research, the study points to a potentially emerging political cleavage between countries in geographic regions expected to be less negatively – or even positively – affected by climate change and those facing substantial projected losses. At the same time, these findings underscore the urgent need for more comprehensive and harmonized panel datasets on mitigation policy ambition – particularly in developing countries, where comparative data on policy ambition remains sparse.

Effects on adaptation policy ambition

Existing research on the relationship between climate extremes and adaptation policy change predominantly relies on case studies, often examining broader policy effects of natural disasters such as tsunamis and earthquakes rather than climate extremes^{10,12,13,16,73–76}. According to this line of research, climate extremes can create windows of opportunity for adaptation policy changes but the policy response to climate extremes varies significantly across different levels of government and political contexts. While some governments adopt more ambitious adaptation policies following severe events, others exhibit only incremental policy adjustments or fail to act altogether.

At the local level, there is case study evidence on the effects of climate extremes on adaptation policies, even though important open questions remain why some communities respond more to climate extremes than others^{21,76–81}. For instance, in the US local and state governments across diverse settings have, in some cases, responded to increasingly severe climate extremes by implementing adaptation policies^{73,76,80}, while in other cases policy inertia can be observed after climate extremes (e.g., in the case of the 2016 flooding in southern West Virginia)⁸². In some cases, climate extremes have been found to be necessary conditions for local adaptation policy adoption, as observed in Switzerland¹⁰ and Sweden⁸³. For instance, in Switzerland, high economic damages from natural disasters further drove adaptation policy ambition, as demonstrated in historical analyses of flood risk management¹⁶. Moreover, Swedish municipalities were found to be more likely to adopt climate adaptation policies when neighboring communities previously experienced floods and implemented similar measures⁸³. This suggests that policy learning and diffusion effects can play a role in shaping adaptation policy responses to climate extremes at the subnational level^{76–80}.

More research on the link between climate extremes and adaptation policy change is also needed on the national and international level. Existing cross-country analyses provide mixed results on whether natural disasters, and particularly climate extremes, lead to substantial policy changes^{13,78,84}. While some evidence suggests that countries experiencing more frequent and intense climate-related hazards allocate greater resources toward adaptation efforts⁸⁴, other studies find no consistent global relationship between disaster frequency and adaptation policy progress, highlighting variability in policy responses among similarly affected nations¹³.

In the narrative review, we find a clear bias towards studies conducted in the US and EU, which investigate the link between climate extremes and adaptation policy change. This constitutes a critical need for more research exploring differences in adaptation policy ambition across developing countries. Despite the growing political attention to adaptation – such as debates over loss and damage funds, which aim to provide financial assistance for adaptation – studies investigating if, how, and under what conditions climate extremes drive higher climate adaptation policy ambition remain scarce. While we identified over 600 studies linking climate extremes and adaptation policy, only 60 focus on developing countries, and after thorough screening, just five were found relevant. These few studies highlight that collaboration⁸⁵ and learning⁸⁶ triggered by extreme events can enable meaningful policy shifts. For example, large-scale disasters can act as critical turning points, disrupting path-dependent, ineffective disaster policy cycles by opening the door to external influence and international cooperation. In Myanmar, the aftermath of Cyclone Nargis prompted a transition from rigid, state-centric governance to more inclusive, polycentric models, though significant challenges related to adaptation policy implementation and path-dependency persist⁸⁷. However, other research cautions that without addressing underlying systemic issues, reliance on extreme events alone may reinforce ineffective policies, emphasizing the need for adaptive, more flexible adaptation policy strategies that move beyond reactive crisis management⁸⁸.

Finally, a recent systematic review of climate adaptation studies summarizes that 58% of the reviewed studies identified (potential) exposure to climate change impacts and climate hazards as a key driver for the adoption of a diverse set of adaptation policies taken by individuals, NGOs, businesses, communities and governments⁸⁹. However, most of the reviewed studies did not explicitly link climate extremes to changes in adaptation policy ambition⁸⁹.

One key reason for this is the inherent difficulty in creating comparable and comprehensive datasets that track adaptation policy change and ambition across regions, levels of government and time^{89–102}. Despite these growing efforts to create comprehensive adaptation monitoring panel datasets^{89–102}, we currently unfortunately still lack harmonized panel datasets to track adaptation policy ambition across countries and time. This is an important research gap to assess the impact of climate extremes on adaptation policy change and ambition. However, developing harmonized panel datasets to systematically track adaptation policy ambition remains a significant challenge due to several interrelated factors. First, there is a fundamental difficulty in defining valid and reliable indicators that allow for meaningful cross-country comparisons of adaptation policy^{100–102}, especially also given the diversity of subnational

adaptation policies that are often not explicitly labeled as adaptation. Second, the limited availability of robust indicators to capture adaptation policy progress^{91,95,101}, compounded by the high context-dependency of adaptation outcomes, further complicates measurement efforts. Third, official sources such as national adaptation plans and UNFCCC National Communications can be subject to self-reporting biases and often focus on plans rather than implemented policy changes, which may distort comparative assessments¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰². Fourth, there are marked disparities in data collection capacities, particularly in developing countries, resulting in uneven coverage and quality⁹². Finally, the analytical complexity of integrating and comparing heterogeneous data sources poses a major obstacle to consistently assessing adaptation policy ambition across time, countries, and governance levels^{89,93,101}.

Recent research has made promising methodological strides in addressing some of these limitations, including the use of advanced machine-learning techniques^{89,93,99,100}. These tools provide an efficient way to process large volumes of policy documents. However, important challenges remain in ensuring that such methods can accurately and consistently capture the level of policy ambition. First, these novel methodological approaches still require clarity on defining valid and reliable measures of adaptation policy ambition. Second, supervised learning methods rely on the availability of temporally fine-grained and comparative raw data of adopted (sub-) national adaptation policies – not merely adaptation plans – as well as high-quality training data. Building such datasets is particularly challenging in developing countries' contexts but remains a critical step for future research in scaling up robust adaptation policy tracking.

In sum, our narrative review shows that there is a clear need for more research on the political mechanisms that drive how and when climate extremes affect climate change mitigation and adaptation policy ambition across different levels of government, regions, and time. As discussed in our narrative review, there is serious bias in the literature towards the EU/US context. This is particularly the case for adaptation policy change^{60,80,103,104,61}. While we find limited evidence for the effects of climate extremes on mitigation policy change, the growing research on adaptation policy provides suggestive results that climate extremes can be an important condition for adaptation policy change, especially also at the subnational level^{93,99,89,100}. Nevertheless, further comparative research is necessary to validate this finding, particularly accounting for how climate extremes change not only the policy density (i.e., number) but also the policy ambition (i.e., stringency) across different contexts. Particularly, we need more research in developing countries where climate impacts will likely be greatest. More research on the political mechanisms that link climate extremes to policy change in developing countries is also relevant as the compounded socio-economic effects of extreme events in such contexts might trigger different political reactions than in higher income countries¹⁷.

Limited Effects of Extreme Weather on Mitigation versus Adaptation Policy

As highlighted in our narrative literature review, only a few comparative large-n analyses on the impact of climate extremes on climate change mitigation policy change exist^{6,9,17}. These studies, however, mainly focus on policy density outcomes – rather than comprehensive panel datasets of climate policy ambition. More research is thus needed to study how various climate extremes affect climate policy ambition across different instruments, sectors, and countries.

To address this gap and test the robustness of results from existing large-n studies^{6,9,17}, we complement our narrative review by conducting illustrative panel regressions and leveraging the most comprehensive internationally harmonized mitigation policy database currently available, which includes measures of policy ambition across multiple sectors, countries and time periods^{8,105} (see details in SI-Section B). Additionally, we integrate this data with an extensive panel dataset on diverse climate-related hazards and climate extremes²³, complemented by qualitative case studies to explore the causal links and political mechanisms driving observed policy changes (see details in SI-Section C). Our illustrative panel analyses focus on the effects of extreme weather on mitigation policy ambition (i.e., stringency) in 51 high-emitting OECD and G20 countries due to the lack of a comprehensive panel dataset on adaptation policy ambition. The case studies include an analysis of selected climate extremes on both mitigation and adaptation policy changes. This also reflects the inherent difficulty of defining, conceptualizing, and measuring adaptation policy ambition. This critical gap needs to be addressed by future research, as outlined in more detail in our narrative review^{89–102}. In addition, future research should provide new harmonized panel data on mitigation policy ambition (rather than merely density), covering also developing countries.

From our illustrative panel regression, we find that the average climate change mitigation policy ambition in the 51 high-emitting OECD and G20 countries exhibits no statistically significant relationship with any of the climate hazard indicators considered, namely drought, heat and extreme precipitation (Figure 2a). This finding holds both for our main multivariate regression model, which considers all climate indicators jointly (red error bars), and for univariate models that consider each indicator separately (grey error bars), as done in previous research⁶. Furthermore, effect sizes implied by the regression are also economically insignificant in magnitude. For instance, a +1°C increase in annual mean temperature is associated with a decrease in ambition (which can range between 0 and 10) by less than 0.02. Similarly, even a 7.5% decrease in soil moisture, as experienced during the 2012 US drought, is associated with a mere 0.01 increase in ambition.

Figure 2: Empirical relationship between climate policy ambition, density and climate extremes. Fig. 2a: Regression coefficients (point estimates as dots, 95% confidence interval based on two-way clustered standard errors as error bars) when regressing a country's average climate change mitigation policy ambition each year on annual temperature and precipitation change and three indicators of extreme climate and weather events (drought, extreme heat, and extreme precipitation). Black and grey dots/error bars denote results from considering all variables jointly ('multivariate model') and only the respective climate indicator ('univariate model'), respectively. We use the ambition of climate change mitigation policies provided by the OECD Climate Actions and Policies Measurement Framework (CAPMF) as outcome variable in our panel regression analysis. The data set comprises 128 policy variables, grouped into 56 policy instruments for relevant economic sectors in 51 countries and the EU between 2000-2022¹⁰⁵. As explanatory variables, we use drought, heat and extreme precipitation indicators as aligned with previous research^{6,9}, based on the OECD's database monitoring exposure to climate-related hazards and events²³, and control for annual temperature and precipitation changes, country and year fixed effects, and country-specific linear time trends. Please note: We control for annual temperature and precipitation due to their strong correlation with climate extremes. These variables have also been linked to socio-economic outcomes, such as economic growth^{106,107}, so we include them as controls to avoid misattributing impacts of climate extremes. In our main specification, we focus on climatic indicators of extremes, rather than their outcomes (e.g., casualties, economic damages), to address endogeneity concerns, as the latter depend on exposure and vulnerability, which are influenced by policy and other factors². More details are provided in the Supplemental Information (SI). **Fig. 2b:** Climate indicator time series for the countries and events described in the case studies; see SI-Section C. Vertical dashed lines denote the respective extreme weather event. **Fig. 2c:** Same as b but for mitigation policy ambition as per the CAPMF data. **Fig. 2d:** Same as b but given the lack of comprehensive adaptation policy ambition here for the cumulative number of adaptation policies by country and year ('policy density') based on the Climate Change Laws of the World database and the Climate Policy Database; see SI-Section C.

Our results align with results from the few existing large-n studies^{6,9,17} that explored the impact of climate extremes on mitigation policy. As outlined above, these previous studies do not use harmonized panel datasets with comparable mitigation policy ambition measures across countries, sectors and time. Hence, our results illustrate that the lack of finding robust effects of climate extremes on climate change mitigation policy change in high-emitting countries shown in previous studies^{6,9,17} is unlikely caused by data limitations but result of a true average null effect. However, we also note that there is a critical lack of comprehensive and harmonized data to measure changes in mitigation policy ambition (not only density) in developing countries

and countries in the geographic South. Recent research has suggested¹⁷ that climate extremes affect climate policy change more in geographic regions that face higher expected climate damages. Yet, the lack of comprehensive panel data on policy ambition limits the investigation of how geography moderates the effects of climate extremes on mitigation policy ambition.

While we do not find a statistically significant link between climate extremes and mitigation policy ambition, previous research has shown that effects may be observable for individual case studies^{9,71}. Therefore, we corroborate the results of our panel regression and qualitatively examine three extreme cases (France, India, US), which all experienced different types of serious climate extremes during the period 2000-2022. We chose these socio-economic and geographically diverse countries based on a most-likely case selection approach because the selected countries are all democracies, which previous research has shown to be more likely to react to climate extremes than autocracies^{6,9,17}. In addition, all three countries experienced from a diverse set of extreme weather indicators the most extreme events and socio-economic impacts, in terms of deaths and costs attributable to climate change according to Newman and Noy¹⁰⁸ (see details in SI-Section C). In essence, if there were effects of severe climate extremes on climate policy change, we should observe them in these extreme cases. France experienced a record heatwave in 2003, which resulted in more than 19,000 deaths. India experienced damaging floods in 2013, with more than a US\$ 1 billion in total damages and more than half a million people affected, while the United States experienced a serious drought event in 2012, leading to more than US\$ 22 billion in total damages¹⁰⁸. Key OECD indicators on climate-related hazards align with each of these climate disasters, showing considerable spikes in extreme heat, soil moisture and extreme precipitation during the disaster year (Figure 2b). If we do not find effects in these three cases where effects should theoretically be most pronounced, it suggests a weak or non-existent causal link between climate extremes and policy change.

The descriptive analysis of the climate change mitigation policy ambition indicator reveals some post-disaster increases across all three countries (Figure 2c), although in some cases, this is merely a continuation of a pre-disaster trend. However, our qualitative evidence indicates a weak connection between the climate extremes and the observed increases in climate change mitigation policy ambition in the three case studies (see SI-Section C).

As discussed above, unfortunately, given the lack of a comparative and harmonized panel database on adaptation policy ambition, we do not have comparable quantitative data to assess changes in adaptation policy ambition in the three cases. For illustrative purposes, in Figure 2d, we depict the cumulative number of adaptation policies by country and year ('policy density') based on the Climate Change Laws of the World Database¹⁰⁹ and the Climate Policy Database¹¹⁰ (see SI-Section C). However, as can be seen in Figure 2d the consistency of the two data sources is low. For instance, in France, the adaptation policy density, as measured by the Climate Change Laws of the World database, starts to strongly increase in the years 2012/2013 while we do not see this trend in the Climate Policy database. Moreover, the policy density measure is not a valid substitute for a comprehensive adaptation policy ambition measure. Our analyses

buttress the narrative review and highlight the need to create more comprehensive panel databases on adaptation policy ambition, covering different sectors and countries⁸⁹⁻¹⁰².

However, despite the lack of large-n evidence on adaptation policy ambition, our qualitative case studies illustrate that the three studied countries chose to implement climate adaptation policies in the post-disaster period, which are specifically aimed at increasing society's resilience to future disasters (SI-Section C). France, for example, adopted a national adaptation strategy in 2006, which makes frequent reference to the 2003 heatwave. This was followed by the adoption of two national climate change adaptation plans in 2011 and 2018, while a third plan is currently under development in addition to many local adaptation plans¹¹¹. Similarly, in the US and Indian case studies we find clear references to the studied climate extremes, namely the US 2012 drought and the Indian 2013 flood disaster, in subsequent national adaptation policies. In contrast to mitigation policy, the examined climate extremes in all three cases increased the political pressure on policymakers to adopt adaptation policies.

Our illustrative case studies of climate change mitigation and adaptation policies also show post-disaster impacts on local climate policy change. For example, in particular, subnational policy changes are observed in India after the flood disaster, such as changes in the local adaptation plan (see SI-Section C). This underlines the need for more granular, subnational data to fully capture the impact of climate extremes on climate change mitigation and adaptation policy^{112,113}, similar to how subnational data has helped identifying climate extremes' effect on economic growth^{114,115}. This is particularly important for the case of adaptation policies that are likely to be adopted by (more affected) subnational governments.

In summary, in line with the results of our narrative review, our illustrative quantitative and qualitative analyses find limited evidence to support the hypothesis that climate extremes drive increased mitigation policy ambition. While such effects are observed for adaptation policies, the results remain inconclusive and require further research. Conversely and crucially, we also do not find robust evidence indicating that climate extremes decrease climate policy ambition. Although much of the existing literature focuses on how climate extremes can foster more stringent climate policies, this directionality is not predetermined. Theoretically, it is equally plausible – perhaps even more so in polarized or institutionally weak contexts – that climate extremes could exacerbate economic downturns and socio-political destabilization.

In such cases, the salience of addressing climate change and its impacts may decrease, while (populist) opposition to climate policy costs rise, meaning that climate extremes could ultimately weaken rather than strengthen climate policy ambition.

Furthermore, the adverse economic impacts of escalating climate extremes may diminish policymakers' ability and willingness to prioritize climate policy, particularly in low-income countries^{115,116}. In such economically constrained contexts, repeated severe extremes and the associated socio-economic damages may prompt policymakers to allocate limited resources toward adaptation rather than mitigation. This raises the question: Can we expect the effects of climate extremes to differ for mitigation and adaptation policy change?

Therefore, based on our narrative review and illustrative analyses, we propose a research framework that addresses key identified research gaps and enables the formulation of testable hypotheses. This is relevant for future research on the political mechanisms linking the effects of climate extremes to policy changes, particularly comparing potential differences in the effects of such event on adaptation versus mitigation policy change.

Research framework: Understanding the political mechanisms linking climate extremes to mitigation and adaptation policy change

Figure 3: Research framework figure on the political effects of climate extremes.

The framework figure illustrates the causal links between climate extremes (i.e. extreme climate and weather events), mitigation and adaptation politics, policies, and their feedback effects. Question marks denote key research gaps. The grey dashed line represents the uncertainty about global and future effects of mitigation policies.

As outlined in our narrative review and illustrative case studies, more research is needed to understand and compare the political mechanisms that link climate extremes to mitigation and adaptation policy change. In our framework Figure 3, we emphasize the central role of politics, in essence the interactions between discourses, mass public, interest group and party positions, in explaining if and how climate extremes can affect mitigation and adaptation policy ambition. In addition, we identify key research gaps (marked with question marks in Figure 3).

First, we underscore the need for further investigation into the politics of adaptation policy, particularly comparative research on how climate extremes influence discourses, public opinion, interest groups, and party positions, as well as policy ambition across diverse political, economic, geographic, and cultural contexts. Currently, the absence of high-quality harmonized panel datasets on (sub-)national adaptation policy ambition limits such analyses. In the narrative review, we have outlined existing challenges and potential pathways to create such databases. Second, we highlight the need to explore interactions between mitigation and adaptation policies given potential political opportunities for strategic policy packaging. Third, as elaborated below, we stress the importance of examining the likelihood of policy changes and interactions between different types of climate policies in response to climate extremes, considering policies' inherent differences in their cost/benefit distributions.

Our framework suggests that the causal pathway between climate extremes and mitigation policy changes is likely longer and more complex compared to adaptation policy changes. Based on existing literature, we argue that mitigation policy changes often require high issue salience and the attribution of socio-economic impacts of climate extremes to climate change. However, given political polarization and motivated reasoning, such attribution is not always prominent in discourse in all socio-political contexts. Nevertheless, this attribution is likely a necessary condition for shifts in public opinion, party positions, and subsequent policy actions. In contrast, adaptation policy changes typically depend on the salience of socio-economic impacts of climate extremes without necessarily requiring their attribution to climate change. This shortens the causal pathway, potentially reduces political polarization risks, and minimizes the influence of motivated reasoning based on actors' prior beliefs about climate change or partisan alignments. In essence, even climate skeptics can support adaptation policies addressing the visible and salient socio-economic impacts of climate extremes without acknowledging human-caused climate change as the root cause. Politically, this should result in greater support for adaptation policies compared to mitigation policies across ideologically diverse groups, which future research could empirically test.

Moreover, for governments and their constituencies, mitigation policies often entail greater uncertainty, primarily due to their inherently global and often mid- to long-term effects, compared to many adaptation policies, which are generally perceived to have more localized impacts (see dashed vs. solid lines in Figure 3). While our framework acknowledges that international agreements – such as the Paris Agreement or funding instruments like the Green Climate Fund – can provide important impetus for the adoption and implementation of national adaptation policies, it also recognizes that many adaptation policies (e.g., local flood protection or urban infrastructure upgrades) tend to produce locally concentrated effects. Even though some adaptation policies may entail concentrated costs, often adaptation policies produce rather concentrated localized benefits but diffused costs. This contrasts with many mitigation policies, which often lead to concentrated costs but diffused benefits. Even though previous studies have shown that free-riding problems tend to be less important than distributional conflicts in explaining differences in national mitigation policy ambition¹¹⁷, the inherent cost-benefit distributions of mitigation policies and the uncertainty surrounding the timing and size of

policy benefits influences beliefs, discourses, public opinion, and elite actor positions¹¹⁸⁻¹²¹. Free-riding arguments and uncertainty about policy benefits are arguably less salient in debates on adaptation policies with their often localized effects. Future research should provide further evidence on how climate extremes and the visible socio-economic impacts from climate extremes reshape actors' beliefs regarding the (un)certainty, effectiveness, and cost/benefit distribution of both mitigation and adaptation policies – especially in politically polarized contexts.

Implications for research and policymaking

Importantly, mitigation and adaptation policies inherently differ in how they distribute costs and benefits across groups and over time, which likely moderates the political effects of climate extremes on policy changes. Building on Wilson’s¹²² policy typology, Figure 4 categorizes climate policies by their cost-benefit distribution, allowing us to derive key hypotheses.

Figure 4 Typology on the distribution of costs and benefits of different climate change mitigation versus adaptation policies. Building on a classical typology Wilson (1974)¹²², the figure illustrates the distribution of costs and benefits for different types of climate change mitigation and adaptation policies, its dependence on the issue salience of climate change and climate extremes (i.e., extreme climate and weather events), and its hypothesized effects on policy change. The framework suggests that as result of more frequent climate extremes, it is easier to adopt adaptation policies with concentrated benefits but diffused costs – e.g., taxpayer-funded levees, flood insurance subsidies or compensation funds – compared to many mitigation policies with concentrated costs but diffused benefits – e.g., fossil fuel phase-outs or emission prices with revenue recycling to citizens or public goods.

First, we hypothesize that many important adaptation policies, such as taxpayer-funded flood protection infrastructure and levees, insurance subsidies, and agricultural compensation funds for extreme weather impacts, with concentrated benefits but typically diffused costs are easier to adopt than most mitigation policies, such as emissions regulations, renewable energy mandates, or carbon pricing. This is because policies with concentrated costs and benefits tend to generally have greater political impacts than those with diffused costs and benefits, at least if diffused costs and benefits are not very salient. Many mitigation policies, except for targeted low-carbon technology subsidies and industrial policies like battery plant grants, impose often high, concentrated, short-term costs while offering rather diffused, long-term, global benefits. In contrast, many key adaptation policies tend to deliver rather near-term, local, and concentrated benefits while spreading costs (often less visibly) across taxpayers.

Second, we propose that organized interest groups facing concentrated costs from mitigation efforts (e.g., fossil fuel industries or coal communities¹²³) may strategically influence discourses around climate extremes to downplay their link to climate change and emphasize mitigation

costs. These groups are also incentivized to sway party positions against adopting stringent mitigation policies in response to climate extremes. However, some of these interest groups – such as farmer associations – can have strategic interests in lobbying for more ambitious adaptation policies, such as targeted compensation funds, that create concentrated benefits.

Third, mitigation policies with diffused benefits (see entrepreneurial and majoritarian politics in Figure 4) often rely on high issue salience to create windows of opportunity for policy entrepreneurs to mobilize public support. Political economy research shows that mass public opinion about climate policies matters most when issue salience is high^{124,125}. In theory, climate extremes can open such opportunities for entrepreneurs to advocate for policies with diffused benefits despite concentrated and diffused costs (e.g., coal phase-outs). However, the presence of influential policy entrepreneurs favoring ambitious mitigation policies is a critical prerequisite. While initial case studies⁵⁷ suggest that strategic policy entrepreneurs can leverage climate extremes to foster policy learning and advance mitigation policies, further comparative and systematic research is needed.

Fourth, climate policy design and framing literature indicates that strategic packaging and framing of policies can enhance feasibility^{124,126–128}. Combining policies to balance costly elements with concentrated benefits for different constituencies can create broader coalitions of support, potentially bridging ideological divides. We hypothesize that strategically packaging mitigation and adaptation policies to offer both concentrated benefits and costs may foster novel coalitions for climate policy change, involving groups like farmer associations and environmental NGOs. Furthermore, packaging adaptation policies together with mitigation policies might also create pathways to build unexpected and ideologically diverse coalitions of concentrated local winners of specific mitigation policies (e.g., targeted subsidies for low-carbon industries, such as battery plant grants) and adaptation policies (e.g., compensation funds for farmers affected by climate extremes) that both offer regionally clustered economic co-benefits. As highlighted in our narrative review, particularly in polarized contexts adaptation policies framed around the local benefits of addressing the impacts of climate extremes (as compared to climate change) might resonate well with politically conservative constituencies that often oppose mitigation policies^{62,63}. Similarly, nature-based mitigation policies (e.g., forest, coastal and wetland preservation) might offer concentrated adaptation co-benefits – e.g., for local communities, industries, and farmers – and thereby increase the feasibility of adopting such mitigation policies. Potentially, also insurance and re-insurance companies can benefit from and lobby for the adoption of such policies in the face of economic losses and risks related to climate extremes. In addition, strategic packaging of mitigation and adaptation policies might offer new pathways for unexpected coalitions in international climate politics. Future research should explore how increasingly frequent climate extremes might drive such reframing and broadening of coalitions around integrated mitigation and adaptation policy packages.

Fifth, policy feedback theory^{129–131} suggests that strategic policy sequencing can facilitate policy change. Evidence shows that targeted subsidies and green industrial policies promoting low-carbon technologies can increase public support and strengthen organized green interest

groups, such as those in renewable energy or electric vehicle sectors^{126,132–136}. These groups, benefiting from stricter regulations and carbon pricing, may shift the political balance over time and political role of climate extremes. Empirical studies indicate that policy feedback can amplify climate policy ambition^{135,137}, and future research should examine how climate extremes might interact with this policy feedback process. For instance, low-carbon technology manufacturer and countries with strong low-carbon industries may strategically leverage salient climate extremes to shift public opinion, elite politics and create novel coalitions in domestic and international climate politics in favor of stricter mitigation policies. In addition, strategic sequencing of adaptation and mitigation policies might be another way of ratcheting-up climate policy action over time. Recent evidence⁵⁹ suggests that voters that benefit from adaptation and are insured against economic losses of climate extremes are less likely to vote for populist parties and tend to support parties in favor of more ambitious climate policies. Concentrated local benefits of adaptation funds and nature-based mitigation might also create new vested interest groups that support more mitigation policy ambition, but further research is needed.

Sixth, institutional contexts likely influence how climate extremes affect both mitigation and adaptation policy changes^{119,138}. In proportional electoral systems with corporatist interest groups mediation, compensation mechanisms may diffuse costs to taxpayers, potentially making interest groups more receptive to leveraging climate extremes as opportunities to justify policy change¹¹⁹. However, research also indicates that salient public demand for climate change mitigation tends to have a greater impact on policy change in majoritarian electoral systems compared to proportional ones^{124,125}. Therefore, salient climate extremes should be more likely to influence policy change in majoritarian systems. We also know less about how institutions shape potential effects of climate extremes on adaptation policy. Future research should thus investigate how institutional frameworks moderate the influence of climate extremes on both mitigation and adaptation policy change.

Finally, geography and its implications for the distribution of projected climate change impacts are likely to play an increasingly important role in shaping the political economy of both mitigation and adaptation policies, and the political impact of climate extremes¹⁷. As recent scholarship has argued¹⁷, the intensification of climate extremes may give rise to new political cleavages between countries in the geographic South, which are projected to experience severe climate damages, and those in the geographic North, which may face comparatively moderate impacts or even potential gains from a warming climate. However, as discussed above, it is equally plausible that escalating climate extremes could trigger economic downturns and socio-political destabilization, thereby undermining, rather than reinforcing, climate policy ambition. Particularly, in developing countries with limited adaptive capacities severe socio-economic consequences of climate extremes^{115,116} may lead governments to prioritize short-term adaptation spending over long-term mitigation investments. While it is already a political reality that countries most affected by climate change are demanding greater adaptation support from less affected countries, the broader implications of geography and its anticipated future climate damages for national and international climate politics remain poorly understood. Little is known about how such geographic asymmetries shape incentives to advance, trade off,

or strategically bundle mitigation and adaptation policies. Yet, addressing such open questions requires larger comprehensive and harmonized datasets on climate mitigation and adaptation policy ambition, especially in developing countries most vulnerable to climate extremes.

In conclusion, our findings indicate that, to date, climate extremes have not strongly and consistently driven mitigation policy change and affected policy ambition – despite some (short-term) political effects. Although initial evidence shows that climate extremes can spur adaptation policy change, data limitations still hinder robust comparative insights into their impact on adaptation policy ambition. We also still lack important evidence on the political mechanisms that link climate extremes to policy change, and how the strategic packaging and sequencing of adaptation and mitigation policies play out in this context. Existing evidence is strongly biased towards higher income contexts. Furthermore, we would like to highlight that the absence of strong past effects does not preclude the possibility that future climate extremes may cross salience thresholds, shaping domestic and international climate politics and policy change in new, so far unobserved ways. Given that such extremes will become more frequent and intense our framework offers a foundation and guidance for future research on the political implications of climate extremes for climate change mitigation and adaptation policy change.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

All relevant data analyzed in this article is provided here:

https://github.com/pwaidelich/climextremes_stringency_submission_v01

Code availability statement

All relevant R code used to analyze the data in this article is provided here:

https://github.com/pwaidelich/climextremes_stringency_submission_v01

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT to proofread the manuscript and correct any grammatical or spelling mistakes. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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